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***Inclusion of Artificial Intelligence
in the Recruitment Process in the
Indian Corporate Sector***

Abstract

As the Indian corporate sector is moving towards digitization, one observes an immense potential for the utilization of artificial intelligence in the human resource department, especially in recruitment. This research paper will be analyzing the future applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the recruitment process and also, how this technology can/will reshape the 'human resources department' (HRD) holistically. The analysis will also be done in order to explore the strength and weakness of the existing corporate sector, to be more precise, the HRD dynamics in accepting AI. The research is done with a future orientation kept in mind, wherein the forecasting is done more on the basis of the current requirements of AI.

Introduction

While the world of recruitment is constantly evolving, it is now in the process of experiencing a real revolution. Companies are now being forced to transform their methods so that they will not be outdistanced by competition and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technological evolution that responds precisely to these new needs.

Each year the talent acquisition executives are expected to hire more and more employees;- recruits who are faster, better and within a limited budget. Most companies' needs are increasing and the race to hire the best candidates is becoming, day by day, more and more intense. So, recruiters are more likely to fail because sourcing is becoming arduous and time-consuming and at the same time, the labour market is suffering from a talent shortage. Hence, today, it

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seems that it is better to entrust ‘recruiting’ to algorithms. And, for this simple reason: ‘artificial intelligence’ AI, a technology, developed by man, to be able to reason like a human being is becoming popular when recruiting employees.

1. What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial Intelligence is a branch of computer science that aims to create intelligent machines¹ that are powered by the ability to learn through the process of solving problems². AI helps the systems to think and act like rational human beings, so as to gain the benefits of performing the work at a faster pace with less computational errors and less fatigue³. AI is the capacity that machines and computers have acquired through the processes of integrating algorithms that are able to simulate and produce the same reasoning as human thoughts with a greater level of accuracy and in a much shorter period of time. The concept of artificial intelligence was introduced, in 1937, by Alan Turing. An English mathematician, who was behind establishing the basis for programmable computers. While trying to answer the question “*Can machines think?*” he developed the Turing test to see if the machine will be able to handle a small talk with another human and understand what is the context of the conversation⁴. Turing was hoping that a computer will pass the test by the year 2000 but none passed this test; however, this test is still used as a reference to the machine’s intelligence and to distinguish what can be computed with its aid and what cannot?

Machines are, now, more powerful with more memory, advanced processor technology and better algorithms that made them able to perform activities like learning, planning, speech recognition, problem solving⁵. So, by mimicking human’s ability to think, machines can now collect information from the real world, use it to learn and acquire knowledge while continuously keep correcting errors and developing new solutions for a better performance.

SIRI, which is now famous, is one such form of a virtual assistant in Apple IOS, Mac IOS, etc. amongst the common end users. The assistant uses voice queries and a natural-language user interface to answer questions, make recommendations, and perform actions by delegating requests to a set of Internet services. Now artificial intelligence is used in different fields and offers a wide range of benefits too. In the healthcare sector, for example, starting in around 2010, AI was used in order to provide clinical decision support, patient monitoring and coaching, automated devices to assist in surgery or patient care, and management of healthcare systems,⁶ in various AI forms like multi layered neural networks (NN), Graphic Processor Units (GPUs) and large labelled data sets have thus given a deep paradigm shift in the service. It is utilized, also, to

advance national defence and public security. Machine learning significantly enhances the ability to predict where and when crimes are more likely to happen and who may commit them.⁷ Algorithmic trading and automated trading systems are very famous, among large investor's institutions, for their capacity to provide fast and correct trading decisions.

In agriculture, machine learning can help farmers to optimize the use of fertilizers to produce larger, healthier fruits and vegetables. Transportation is likely to be one of the first domains in which the general public will be asked to trust the reliability and safety of an AI system for a critical task.⁸ Equipped with sophisticated sensors, data and applications like real-time sensing and prediction of traffic route calculations, smart cars will now be better and safer drivers than individuals. Not only in transportation, machines with their capacity to learn and carry out an enormous number of tasks at the same time, are doing things better than their human counterparts in different areas. These small examples show what kind of changes and ameliorations are brought about by Artificial Intelligence. So, what about human resource management?

2. AI and Human Resources

In 2016, AI funding reached a high record of \$5.02 billion compared to just \$589 million in 2012 according to Cloud Tweaks report.⁹ Companies, nowadays, spend a huge amount of time and money on AI trying to develop new solutions that will help them to increase their productivity and ameliorate the performance of their core and support functions.

While dealing with employees, the Human Resource Department (HRD) has to analyse multiple variables that can be quantifiable and qualitative. Many times, the inability to decode huge and complicated data may lead to an oversight of some important parameters and failed Human Resources (HR) strategy. This requirement has led to a demand of AI in Human Resource Management (HRM). Some companies like Pepsico and L'Oreal have made some notable changes in HR through AI. With applications like Natural Linguistic Processing (NLP) for tracking the behavioural patterns of employees, virtual employee assistants like "Personik", the organization is finding it easy to manage employee engagement and facility management. The ability to analyse and to provide analytics and metrics are the most widely preferred aspects of AI, among HR professionals and managers according to a survey held by HR.com. One of the most interesting findings, in this survey, is that HR leaders think that human resources represent a high potential of AI and they are expecting that machine-learning applications will be utilized in many HR functions specially.¹⁰

- Time and attendance
- Talent Acquisition
- Training and development
- Compensation and Payroll

Jonathan Kestebaun, executive director of Talent Tech Labs, says “Implementing AI software simply eliminates mundane tasks and time-consuming data analysis to serve as an ongoing problem-solver for HR. These digital assistants will save HR pros from falling into an inevitable pit of bias while providing predictive, impactful data and identification of trends to solve recurring problems in the HR process.”¹¹ HR is one of the targeted functions by artificial intelligence start-ups. Surprisingly, in spite of the high potential of AI, the current usage rate of AI in HR in India is still low but predicted to increase in the upcoming 5 years. Most of today’s debates are focused on whether automatization and artificial intelligence will lead to a massive dismissal of employees leading to managers having to deal with downsizing in the nearest future, or whether they will create more jobs than destroying existing jobs during downsizing. So, managers will be, from now on, more concerned about orientation and career management. It is certain that HR has the duty to ask the right questions associated with the future changes of the business. This proactive approach should be supported by the development of employees’ skills. The mission of HR is to rethink each position to prepare for the automatization of the tasks in order to reorient them based on their new added value.

3. AI and Recruitment

One of the most obvious applications of artificial intelligence, in HR, is recruitment. To deal with a mass of candidates, artificial intelligence now facilitates the management of candidates and candidatures by using algorithms. In job offers, the goal is no longer simply to target a ‘metier’ but rather a panel of skills. Thus, the Big Data, processed by algorithms, makes it possible to refine the criteria of selection and to specify the researches to find the ideal candidate. The use of AI, in recruitment, is increasing and this is due to 3 main reasons¹²:

- ***Good Data is Finally Available:*** The increased use of social media like Facebook, LinkedIn and the rise of subscribers in job boards helped to ascend available and valuable data that can be used for sourcing and screening. It, also, made access to a large scale of candidates easy and efficient, which means more data that makes AI bear the imminent promise of an automatic analysis and management.¹³

- ***Machine Learning has Matured (Enough)***: There was a dramatic shift related to how software was delivered. Over the last half a century, or so, most software would assist one in doing the job a little bit faster and a little bit more accurately but with the new algorithms, one just needs to describe what one wants done and the software will actually do it. Moreover, in the recent past, business processes were able to manage, only, small data sets and they were used more for explaining statistical, formal models, while today, with stronger and complex algorithms, machines are, now, capable of predicting and explaining; they are, also, able to use “unstructured” data like video, audio, and free text.¹⁴
- ***Predictive Analytics has become a Competitive Necessity***: Predictive analytics involves a set of various statistical (data mining) techniques used to predict uncertain outcomes.¹⁵ Applying ‘predictive people analytics’ is comparatively new but early adopters showed us some astonishing results that actually helped the companies to save or earn a lot of money. Using predictive analytics is a key aspect for companies to survive in a competitive environment. For HR departments, “*analytics is one such tool that can help them predict employees’ performance based on historical and real-time data.*”¹⁶ And it can also help the companies for the recruitment process, like for example, by predicting a candidate’s personality just by analysing his Facebook profile, according to a study made in 2012 by Kluemper, Rosen & Mossholder.

By using AI and machine learning, it’s, now, possible to forecast data and understand the phenomenon that surrounds most employees. Predictive people analytics is a game changer for HR managers and for the companies that are, always, seeking for more productivity, more control and a better understanding of the performance’s variables, so they can cope up and keep being competitive.

Every part of the recruiting process can be enhanced with AI, from Advertising to sourcing, to screening, to scheduling the interviews, to selection, to engaging and retaining talents. Recruiters can be assisted with Artificial Intelligence that can provide critical data to them, components to predict analytics and information that will help them to comprehend, evaluate, and make the right decisions.

Advertisement

AI start-ups have developed different assisting solutions that will help the hiring executive while publishing the job offers. Textio is an AI assistant, trained to provide reviews and score the language used in the advertisement copy and looks at how positive it is and then adopt the provided suggestions to improve the attractiveness of the advertisements and differentiate it from other

competitors.¹⁷ Artificial intelligence applications, for example, Recruitz.io, can also help to find the most suitable online channel for ads and the best timeframe to publish and reach a large pool of candidates.

Sourcing and Screening

When it comes to tracking future candidates and matching the right person to the co-related job description, you can find a lot of AI products that are able to facilitate the talent acquisition executive job. Intelligent machines can automatically search for adequate job seekers by collecting information from social media sites like Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter, job boards sites or companies' sites and quickly identify the potential of each candidate. In addition to that, it can also easily reach passive candidates with personalized messages at the right time¹⁸.

HR managers can use AI ability to quickly assess and analyse text or video patterns to shorten the screening process. In other terms, AI-applications are able to extract information from CVs, conclude the degree of concordance based on job requirements, measure the candidate's experience, run background checks and rank them according to the need. Using video interviews, the assessment can go further and evaluate the applicants on a large scale by adding sentiment analysis and computational linguistics.

Engage and Reengage

Engaging your future applicants may begin way before starting the recruitment process by using artificial intelligence as a virtual assistant.¹⁹ Cognitive computing can use company's local data, like for example resignation rate, retirements turnover rate and attrition risk, to predict trends and the need in term of qualifications and skills and then engage customized conversation to convince potential applicants to join your company.

AI assistant is also able to inform different candidates about the progress of their situation and respond to their questions related to the recruitment process. It can also re-engage candidates, especially the ones who got rejected, by notifying them about the job offers that match their profiles.

Selection

Intelligent computers and machines are now able to enhance the recruitment process performance due to their effectiveness and their capacity to reduce the errors that can happen during a cognitive decision²⁰ by providing almost 100 percent accurate information during the selection process. Chatbots facilitate the process of decision-making, and collecting and evaluating information about different applicants, by maintaining a productive conversation and by being

able to conduct cognitive and personality tests, measure their motivation, their engagement and their expectations and match it with the expectations of the teams that they might join.²¹

Scheduling Interviews

AI start-ups are generating assisting solutions that can schedule interviews, meetings and negotiate on the recruiter's behalf. So, once the HR professional chooses his settings, the intelligent assistant's first task is to understand what exactly the constraints are; what the preferences are, and then remove the HR professional from the conversation to start a very human-like dialogue back and forth with one or more participants to negotiate with them and invite them for the interviews.

“Onboarding”

Engaging and conserving employees is one of the biggest HR's concern;²² AI applications can offer customized “onboarding” procedures for every single position and can provide well-planned programs, dedicate enough time to each of the employees and make the retention rates go up.

AI can also help to reduce the time accorded to the hiring process by executing quickly and effectively, monotonous operations related to scanning, evaluating applications and quickly eliminating a high number of inadequate candidates. And, also, it will advance the performance of HR practitioners by reducing poor hiring decisions and the cost related to that. Intelligent applications will provide recruiters with a greater insight on candidates by gathering multi-sourced data that will help to inform if the candidate is adequate for the position at a particular company.²³

“*AI will likely replace tasks rather than jobs in the near term...*” – a 100-year study on Artificial Intelligence:²⁴ In other words, this means that the main purpose of applying AI in recruitment is not to replace the role of a recruiter by a computer but to automate administrative, repetitive and time-consuming tasks, that can be apprehended by machines, in a way that will increase the efficacy and the efficiency of the hiring process. It will also help HR professionals to focus more on the IQ aspects of their job, and try to understand why an employee is leaving, or try to create a conversation package to attract more talent, or try to convince talented recruits that their company is the best for the candidate and thus to concentrate more on human judgement and the interaction part of the recruitment process.

4. What are the Limitations of Applying AI on Recruitment?

1. ***The Cloning Effect is a Real Disadvantage:*** One of the aspects that

HR pros need to be aware of while integrating Artificial intelligence in the recruitment process, is the cloning effect, due to the tendency of recruiting similar profiles shaped by the same experience and qualifications. Indeed, the recruiter will acquire highly operational workers but will be deprived of innovation, diversity, fidelity and critical reasoning which can lead to a kind of stagnation and resulting poor performance.²⁵

2. ***Racist Robots:*** AI needs huge amounts of information, provided by Bigdata, in order to learn. So, companies need to be careful of what they feed to AI because they might end up with biased candidates' information hand outs to the machines and, then, apply it in their hiring process. Because of the defective information, the decisions made by the computer might be racist²⁶ or show some tendencies like preferring masculine names²⁷ or with any other kind of discrimination related to genders, age, races, etc....
3. ***Inability to Read and React Appropriately to Some Human Aspects:*** Although AI has reached a certain degree of intelligence, they are still unable to assess and understand some features of human speech, languages, signals²⁸ and emotions (for example using emojis, stickers or GIFs in a conversation)²⁹, which can lead to a misinterpretation and thereby, wrong decisions, especially, while using chatbots, speech recognition soft wares or video analytics.
4. ***Inadequate Decision-making Ability:*** AI tools can't perform alone or make decisions outside what is already programmed in the algorithms and can be wrong because they might not be able to detect the nuances and the context as humans do.³⁰ In other words, even though AI can manipulate different forms of data and replicate³¹ humans reasoning, it is inept to make as good decisions as humans. Consequently, intelligent computers need continuous monitoring from the user, which involves certain knowledge about how to use this new technology, and actually, most of the HR managers are not yet ready and they lack the main skills to utilize this technology.

5. How Indian Organisations should Use and Integrate AI in Recruitment?

Today, the world's biggest economies are all aware of the importance of artificial intelligence, the opportunities that it offers and in order to benefit from the profitability of AI related-activities they rushed to implement strategies and guidelines, especially USA, China, UK, Japan, France. Those strategies imply an increase of scientific research in this area, a development of skills and

talents that can handle this new technology, an intensification of digital infrastructure to make networks connectivity faster and safer and finally the establishment of incentives and tax benefits to businesses and AI's start-ups to encourage innovations and new ideas.

The second largest population in the world (India) is, actually, very concerned by the inevitable effects of AI on society and on the economy. Given the unique identity of this country, which is characterized by a social and cultural diversity and its distinguished economic and political situation, India represents an ideal territory for the development of AI applications. However, it also has a very vulnerable environment, on one hand, to the risks that, artificial intelligence and automation of tasks might represent due to the size and the variety of the population, and on the other hand, to the challenges, starting from income inequality and caste-based discrimination to linguistic diversity IA³², and this makes applying AI in India hard, and not exactly appropriate for some problems.

In response to this situation, the Indian government started with the implementation of a task force of artificial intelligence under the Ministry of Commerce and Industry in 2017. The objective of creating this task force was to determine the strategic direction for artificial intelligence development in India.³³ The focus of the public sector is on developing AI in 3 main sectors. Agriculture and Healthcare to increase the prosperity of the population using Artificial Intelligence technology and, also, an Indian Languages Project was installed, for a long-term period, to help the development of NLP's (Natural Language Processing) applications, like conversational, general and career counselling through 'chatbots' and assistants, conversing, in 22 Indian languages.³⁴

In the private sector, Indian start-ups and tech firms, have started integrating AI in their products and services but India is still far behind compared to the other developed countries. The race to acquire the full potential of Artificial Intelligence technology is still long and India has far to go. According to the reaction from Mr. Avi Patchava, Vice President, Data Sciences, ML and AI – InMobi, India has a lot of knowledge as far as picking up a review of India's greatest qualities as a nation's capacity to use AI is concerned. Avi conveniently summed up what he accepts are India's three greatest qualities to confront the forthcoming AI interruption:

- “India has a wealth of designing ability which has been prepared throughout the most recent 2 decades which should be streamlined and focused into a new direction because of its automation of IT services. This centre base of building is required to get things done with AI at scale”.

- “Data – We have a nation that is quickly moving towards digitization – For instance, the Aadhar or UIDAI Project in India is the biggest ever one of a kind, identifier venture on the planet. India is effectively pushing increasingly more and more into making open datasets and the fact that it is a ‘majority rules’- system, assists it with this reality over China where open information might be confined only to the legislature”
- Over 3 million individuals who are either specifically occupied with the IT administrations around the world are from India. It has a talented workforce, however with the required standard, which makes it a key to opening doors for machine learning and computerization. The IT administrations players like Infosys, Wipro and so on have seen this opportunity and have begun to create rearrangements to embrace AI”.

Keeping the above observations in mind, and as per Madhu Gopinathan, Vice President, Data Science at MakeMyTrip, India’s largest online travel company, there were two concern areas for creating the compatibility for AI; a lucrative salary in the IT sector and the availability of data.

As per his interview, “Academic and Industrial collaboration is a serious issue in India. Although we have a lot of universities, the incentives are skewed towards the corporate sector. For example, people like me who have an understanding of the technology may not be inclined to teach the next generation at universities, since working at the larger companies is far more lucrative today.”

With the dynamics of inclusion of artificial intelligence, there is one factor undisputed is the huge potential of involving AI in human resource department for redefining the functionalities.

AI technology is reshaping the processes and the functions in a lot of sectors. A few Indian applications, that target optimising recruitment, are available, like for example *Belong.co* a Bengaluru start-up that assists companies and simplifies their hiring process by publicly looking for data of talent on online community networks and social media to intelligently match candidates to relevant opportunities and jobs.³⁵ This start-up has as clients, companies such as Cisco, Paypal, Adobe, ABB, Tesco, ThoughtWorks and Tavant Technologies, most of which are MNCs (Multinational Companies); some of their other clients include, Flipkart, Myntra, Ola, InMobi and Directi. *Belong.co* and other few Indian applications which, are providing HR solutions that help their clients to acquire the best talent and put them in an advantaged position in a job market characterised by an intense competition between local enterprises and MNCs.

A 2018 study made by PWC, demonstrates that the high cost of AI technology and the lack of technical ability and quality data are the main barriers to AI integration in Indian businesses, as is shown in the figure below.

Artificial intelligence is still new, and using this technology is still relatively expensive but the prices will start decreasing when AI will attend a certain maturity and therefore, it will be affordable for most Indian companies but this

Source: PwC report on 'AI in India – hype or reality?'³⁶

is not the only concern, though Indian companies are facing issues collecting funds for their AI pilot projects which slows the progress of AI in India. The lack of skilled workforce, unlike other domains, AI/recruitment business is powered by huge available data coming from social media, like Facebook pages, LinkedIn profiles and others, that provide valuable information that is ready to be used in sourcing and screening potential candidates.

AI applications can cover different parts of the recruitment process, starting from sourcing applicants to the on-boarding process. Facing this multitude of solutions, the Indian HR pros need to decide in which area they need to include the help of intelligent machines, especially, when the cost of AI applications is still so high. To decide that recruiters should take into consideration, first, the size of the company, if an enterprise has a huge staff and if they are recruiting constantly or not. Second, they should think about where they are facing problems? Where time is wasted the most? Managers need to find parts that are time-consuming and enhance them with AI tools to make effective time management.

AI systems are specialized in accomplishing one task intelligently and quickly which made the demand on digital services escalate due to its applicability in multiple domains of activity. Integrating this technology in the company's recruitment process can present multiple opportunities that need to be well-thought-out while taking into consideration, the companies manpower needs and the individual particularities of their recruitment process.

Conclusion

The summarization of the research can lead to a definite conclusion about the undisputed potential of artificial intelligence. In the early stages, there is a tremendous requirement of information gathering and analysis from the side of the recruiter as the job seeker also collects and collates data about the organization to create a mental representation and analyse and compare with their own satisfaction. This aspect can be successfully covered by AI. This technology will help recruiters to focus more on the intellectual, human and social aspects of their jobs while eliminating repetitive and time-consuming tasks and reduce all forms of errors that can occur while selecting or hiring a candidate. AI technology however, also represents a number of limits, mainly related to its huge independency to the data fed to this technology (Cloning effect and racist AI) or to its incapacity to understand some features of human speech, languages, signals and emotions, which can lead to wrong results and affect the decision-making process.

There is a yawning gap between the future needs of AI in the corporate sector and the current academic structure of academic institutes of information technology. The gap gets extended because of the speedy evolution of technology in implementation and the curriculum designing and forecasting doesn't match the pace till now in India.

As India is dealing with 400+ dialects of languages, there is again an immense crisis of adopting the same system even within the states. A similar situation can be considered though as the solution as an easy adaptability factor by the end user.

Therefore, considering the overall scenario of the Indian corporate sector, which is immensely reflected in the human resources department, it can be judged on the basis of the technology adaptability of the sector. There were some sectors which could be identified as having huge adaptability potential such as the IT and ITeS (Information Technology enabled Services) sectors which can be conceived as low hanging fruits of the benefits of AI. Also considering the workforce age of the country there are high chances the "internet generation" will take over 50% of the population with the median age of 35 by 2020. The generation always was inclined towards technology and the inclusion of same in form of AI will enhance their work capabilities and effectiveness.

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